

Interview - Met Office User Experience

Authors:

Poppy Townsend

Affiliations:

NERC Environmental Data Service, Science and Technology Facilities Council

About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

This document describes an interview undertaken as part of the context setting work. You can find a synthesis of all other interviews here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102198>

Interview: Met Office User Experience

Meeting date: 12/03/2025

We spoke to the User Experience lead at the Met Office. The team has grown from 4 to 20 people in the last few years as the Met Office has shifted to be more user focused. They have a background in user research and innovation.

We also spoke to an applied scientist working with customers (e.g. private sector, government) to make climate science delivered at the Met Office relevant to them. They have 16 years of experience at the Met Office working with stakeholders and users.

Shifting to user centred design ways of thinking at the Met Office

- Previously the Met Office was more output focussed rather than outcome/user focused
- Ensuring people understand what user-centred design is - not just asking users what they want but discovering what they need.
- Often the focus is on what the customer wants and not the user
- Previous mindset - build a thing and the measurable outcome is that it exists, not the impact it has or decisions made following on from its use
- UK climate resilience programme - upscaling climate services
 - Some of these projects take a long time to develop
 - E.g. 9 months speaking to one local authority to build a service- can't repeat this with the next local authority who are also interested. There is a need for time/funding for scaling these services from the outset

- Local authority climate service - scaled up version of this initial project
- Creating application ready data
- Would be great to have some time to assess what the need is and is it common across multiple similar users - build a single tool for this instead of building it over again

Challenges

- User centred design practice has grown in the Met Office from technology dept. - challenge to implement in other departments
- Too many tools doing the same thing that don't get maintained properly, they are not built from outside in - 'disjointed legacy systems and services'
- defining the difference between customer and user
- Teams don't always have resource to invest in user research
- Mindset shift needed - previously when applying for funding it is already decided what is going to be built - GDS requires a more agile approach - ability to stop if not working, shift focus, flexibility - but need to be able to structure and fund this
- Trying to be user-centred and agile when this doesn't match funding and structure
- Met Office has competitors - other providers can do similar things, makes user-centred services very important
- Expectation management - users don't fully appreciate the work required in the background for services that look simple on the surface
- Can articulate what we want to do better than who our users are and what they need
- gov.uk blogs - should they publish here?

Funding

- Shorten funding is fine if open to discovery - route changes, stopping, pivoting
- Funding for a phase rather than funding based on specific outputs
- Invest in short validating stage of funding
- More iterative funding
- Not necessarily the short funding but the sporadic nature that causes issues
- Flexibility - focus on outcomes not outputs - what we want to change and allow research to lead what we need to do to get that change
- 'Begin with the end in mind'

Met Office UCD team

- Centralised team that gets funded to work on projects full time
- Sat within UCD team but all working time / task management in project team funding them
- Every person is dedicated to a single project
- They have external suppliers that can provide people part time work on smaller projects
- UCD should be integrated from the start to ensure project is user focused from start
- More request that resource available now that there are example projects that have shown the value of it

Connection with our work

- Met Office are building similar internal libraries to the toolkit
- Implementing/responding to Government Service Standards
 - Teams don't have resource to invest in user research
- Met Office has a community of practice - happy to share both ways
- Open to collaborate: e.g. we have users that need a tool but we're not the best people to work on it